

Pp3c14_17190V3.1 CDS|P.patens DDGYEAKLGDFFGLAA-IVP-L-KATHATT-EVLACTIGFIAPE
 Pp3c10_16000V3.1 CDS|P.patens DEGYEAKLGDFFGLAA-VVP-L-KATHATT-EVLACTIGFIAPE
 CepurGG1.2G159700.1 CDS|C.purp DERFEAKLGDFFGLAA-IVP-L-KATHAST-NVIAGTIGFIAPE
 CepurGG1.3G182400.1 CDS|C.purp TDDLEAKLGDFFGLAA-ILP-D-TATHGST-EHLACTIGYIAPE
 Mapoly0115s0067.1 CDS|M.polymo DENYTAHLADFFGLAK-VLP-G-ADTHVTT--GVAGTVGYIAPE
 Smoell_97168 CDS|S.moellendorf DEELEAHLGDFFGLAK-ALP-D-GMTHVTT--QVAGTIGYIAPE
 Dicom.02G032700.1 CDS|D.compla DENMGAHLGDFFGLAR-LIP-D-DKTHITT--GVAGTVGYIPPE
 Dicom.02G032800.1 CDS|D.compla DEDMEAHLGDFFGLAR-QIP-D-DKTHITT--GVSCTVGYIPPE
 Gb_16489|cds-8-10000835-100032 DDNFEAHVADFFGLAK-AVP-E-AATHITS-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 Gb_35408|cds-3-387812923-3878 DDNFEAHVADFFGLAK-AIP-E-AATHITS-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 Gb_18261|cds-8-10098833-10101 DDDFEAHVADFFGLAK-AIP-E-SVTHITS-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 Thup1.29378695s0004.1 CDS|T.pl DEDFEAHVADFFGLAK-ALP-E-AATHATS-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 Thup1.29380329s0004.1 CDS|T.pl DENFDAHVADFFGLAK-ALP-D-AATHATS-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 Thup1.29377027s0006.1 CDS|T.pl DENFDAHVADFFGLAK-ALP-D-TATHATS-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 Thup1.29379777s0016.1 CDS|T.pl DENFDSHVADFFGLAK-ALP-D-TATHDTY-SYVAGTMGYIAPE
 AmTr_v1.0_scaffold00166.7 CDS| DDEMEARIADFFGLAR-TMP-DNANTHITT-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 Aqcoe5G387700.1 CDS|A.coerulea DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-AMP-D-ADTHVTT-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 VIT_217s0000g09710.1 CDS|V.vin DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-AVP-D-ANTHVTT-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 Lsat_1_v5_gn_4_78640.1 CDS|L.s DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-SIP-D-ADTHMTS-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 HanXRQr2_Chr09g0411241|SOBIR1 DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-SIP-D-ADTHMTS-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 HanXRQr2_Chr16g0727251|SOBIR1 -----E-SIP-N-ADTHIQTFSSVAGTLGYMAPE
 Lsat_1_v5_gn_1_28600.1 CDS|L.s DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-SIP-E-AQTHMTS-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 HanXRQr2_Chr04g0148411|SOBIR1 DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-SIP-G-GDTHMTS-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 HanXRQr2_Chr02g0050661|SOBIR1 DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-SIP-E-ADTHMTS-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 orange1.1g006739m CDS|C.sinens DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-AMP-D-AQTHITT-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 orange1.1g041655m CDS|C.sinens DHDMEARISEFFGLAK-VFP-E-AHTHITT-SDVVGTVAGYIAPE
 orange1.1g009595m CDS|C.sinens DDDMEARIADFFGLAR-LMP-D-GHAQVST-SIVAGTVGYIAPE
 orange1.1g036970m CDS|C.sinens DDDMEARISEFFGLAK-QIP-N-GRTRTTT-WSLAETVGYIAPE
 orange1.1g014140m CDS|C.sinens DDDMEARISEFFGLAK-RIP-D-GHTRTTT-WSLAGTVGYIAPE
 orange1.1g040898m CDS|C.sinens DDDMEARISDFGHGK-LMP-D-GHAQITV-KCMVGTMGYMAPE
 orange1.1g040480m CDS|C.sinens DDDMEARISGFDLAI-LMP-D-GLTQIDT-MYVVGTPRYIAPE
 Vigun09g096400.1 CDS|V.unguicu DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-AMP-D-YKTHVTT-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 orange1.1g046907m CDS|C.sinens DDDIEARISGFFGFAR-AIP-D-AHTHITT-SNVVGTVVEYIAPE
 Solyc06g071810.1.1 CDS|S.lycop DDDMEARVADFFGLAK-AVP-D-AHTHITT-SNVAGTVGFIAPPE
 MgTOL.D1881.1 CDS|M.guttatus_T DDEMEARIADFFGLAK-EMP-D-FKTHVTT-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 MgTOL.O0343.1 CDS|M.guttatus_T DDEMEARIADFFGLAK-AIP-D-SHTHVTT-SHVAGTLGYIAPE
 Cucsa.196310.1 CDS|C.sativus v DDGMEARIADFFGLAK-AMP-D-AQTHMTA-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 AT2G31880.1 AtSOBIR1-1|A.thali DDDMEARISDFGLAK-AMP-D-AVTHITT-SHVAGTVGYIAPE
 Solyc03g111800.2.1 CDS|S.lycop DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-AVP-D-AHTHITT-SNVAGTIGYIAPE
 Acora.01G062800.1 CDS|A.americ DDDLEARIADFFGLAK-AVP-D-ANTHVTT-SAVAGTVGYIAPE
 orange1.1g011360m CDS|C.sinens NDDMEACISDLGLAM-AIP-D-GYTRVLI-SYVLGTMAYIAPE
 orange1.1g037084m CDS|C.sinens DDGMEARISDFGLAK-LMP-D-GHTRIRI-TTVAGTTGYVAPE
 Nycol.B00799.1 CDS|N.colorata DDDLEPRIADFFGLAK-SMP-D-MYTHATT-SNVAGTFGYIAPE
 Zosma04g02530.1 CDS|Z.marina v DDDLEAKITDFGLAK-AIP-D-ANTHMTT-SNVAGTVGYIAPE
 GSMUA_Achr2T06010_001 CDS|M.ac DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-EMP-D-ANTHITA-SKVAGTLGYISPE
 LOC_Os06g18000.1 CDS|O.sativa DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-AMP-D-AHTHMTT-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 Sobic.010G120800.1 CDS|S.bicol DDDLEPRIADFFGLAK-AMP-D-SHTHVTA-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 Zm00001d045785_T001 CDS|Z.mays DDDLEARIADFFGLAK-AMP-D-SHTHVTA-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 Bradilg43417.1 CDS|B.distachyo DDDMEARIADFFGLAK-AMP-D-AQTHVTT-SHVAGTMGYIAPE
 MgTOL.A0684.1 CDS|M.guttatus_T DGEMEARIADFFGLAV-MVS-DAADTHVSA-SNLVGTVGYIALE
 GSMUA_Achr6T28170_001 CDS|M.ac DDDLNARISDFGLAK-VVP-D-TASGPMR-SGLKGTIGYIAPE
 GSMUA_Achr6T28180_001 CDS|M.ac DDDLNPRISDFGLAK-VVP-D-TVSGSMR-SGVAGTIGYIAPE
 GSMUA_Achr8T28620_001 CDS|M.ac -----EMMSGTVAS-SNVAGTLGYIAPD
 Aco027508.1 CDS|A.comosus v3|S DGDLPRIADFFGLAK-LVPGDAISGPMNS-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 Aco009339.1 CDS|A.comosus v3|S DRDLNARIADFFGLAK-LVPGDAISGPMNS-SNVAGTLGYIAPE
 Apun_EVM_utg0001171.20|Anthoce DDKFEPHIGDFGLAK-MLQ-D-GRTHASA-TNVAGTLGFIAPPE
 AagrOXF_EVM_utg0000281.95|Anth DDKFEPHIGDFGLAK-MLQ-D-GRTHASA-TNVAGTLGFIAPPE
 Azfi_s0148.g053104-mRNA-1-cds| DEAMEAHIGDFGLAK-LVR-DDS-THVTG-SNWVGTVGYVAPE
 Sacu_v1.1_s0116.g021069-mRNA-1 DDNMEARIGDFGLAK-AMA-DPSFTHVTG-SNWAGTVGFAAPE
 Gb_03580|cds-5-488767202-4887 DDDFEPHLSDFGLGK-LMP-N-SGA-----AGYIAPE
 Thup1.29382036s0003.1 CDS|T.pl DDNYEPHLADFFGLSKAIMP-N-SGA-----AGYVAPE
 AmTr_v1.0_scaffold00016.126 CD DEEFEPRLGDLGLIR-VLP-N-LGK-----VGSGYTAPE
 Aqcoe5G324000.1 CDS|A.coerulea DAEFEPRLGDCGLAH-LMP-N-WGR-----T----TSSYTAPE
 VIT_201s0150g00020.1 CDS|V.vin DAEFEPRLADCGGLAK-LMP-N-LDR-----A----ASGYSAPPE

orange1.1g047245m CDS|C.sinens
Vigun05g020600.1 CDS|V.unguicu
Cucsa.095680.1 CDS|C.sativus v
Solyc05g023760.3.1 CDS|S.lycop
AT5G13290.1 AtCRN|A.thaliana T
GSMUA_Achr5T21380_001 CDS|M.ac
Aco015072.1 CDS|A.comosus v3|C
LOC_Os01g70260.2 CDS|O.sativa
Traes_3B_A7CC68640.1 CDS|T.aes
Bradi2g59470.1 CDS|B.distachyo
Sobic.003G411800.1 CDS|S.bicol
Zm00001d042268_T001 CDS|Z.mays
Acora.03G199100.1 CDS|A.americ
Lsat_1_v5_gn_4_1681.1 CDS|L.sa
HanXRQr2_Chr12g0564651|CRN-1
Nycol.G00930.1 CDS|N.colorata
Zosma05g09280.1 CDS|Z.marina v
MgTOL.K1067.1 CDS|M.guttatus_T
Cucsa.349230.1 CDS|C.sativus v

DAEFTPRLADFGGLAK-LMP-G-SLI-----A-----TSAYSAPPE
DGDFFPRLADYGLAK-LLP-N-LDR-----G-----TSLYTPPE
DGEYEPRLADCGLPK-LFS-N-LNM-----AS----TSAYTSPE
DAEFPRLADCGLAK-IIP-T-LNL-----PA----ASNYGPPE
DSEFPRLADCGLAK-IMP-S-SHT-----A-----VSCYSAPE
DEGFEPRLGDFGLA--MLE-N-SRL-----DTPSTATHYVAPE
DEGFEPRLGDCGLKR-LVM-A-GNF-----DV-AASAHYVAPE
DEDFEPRLADCGLVSR-LIA-S-GSA-----DPELASSLYSAPE
EEGFEPVLADCGVAR-LID-S-GSP-----DPQSSGSLYTAPE
DEGFEPILADCGVAS-LID-S-GPA-----DPESFGSVYAAPE
DEGFEPILTDCGVAR-LIA-A-SSG-----DPELCSGLYAAPE
DEGLEPLLADCGVAR-LIA-A-GSG-----DPELCTGLYAAPE
DEEFPMLADCGVAR-LVS-D-SGG-----AA-VGGFAYVAPE
DADFPRLGDCGLAR-IMH-T-FDG-----RS-----SAYNAPE
DADFPRL---ALSA-LAN-T-FHGL-----RSPQPPAPYYAPE
DDDFEPRLADYGLLG-LMQ-E-TGR-----TSAYVAPE
DDEFEPRLADCGLVLR-LLC-G-NAN-----FYSTYAAPE
GSQFEPRLADCGLAP-ILP-D-FSR-----AGSCYTGPE
DAEFPRLVDFGLTN-LIP-D-FHT-----SPSLYTAPE